

IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGINEERS AND BUILDERS

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Annotation. The development of modern society, penetrating into the information environment of development, requires consideration of the role and importance of information and Information Processes, new technologies of information processing, telecommunications based on computer systems. At present, information technologies are widely used, which surround all spheres of production activity and a certain part of our life.

Keywords: engineers-builders, education, concept, education, professional, technical.

Training of future engineers-builders is one of the most urgent tasks of the National concept of education, aimed at providing the education system with personnel. As noted above, the novelty of higher education institutions, their difference from previous professional technical educational institutions, is manifested in new requirements for pedagogical personnel. In this regard, the need arises for the development of specific software methodological components of teacher training in higher educational institutions. A systematic, comprehensive approach to the problem under study covers the tasks of separating the requirements for a specialist, new principles of their preparation, identifying meaningful, organizational and process components based on a personal and activity approach. Professional competence is the acquisition by a specialist of the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of professional activities and the ability to apply them at a high level in practice.

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information and Information Processes, new technologies of information processing, telecommunications based on computer systems.

At present, information technologies are widely used, which surround all spheres of production activity and a certain part of our life. The implementation of such technologies provides an opportunity for automatic processing of Information Exchange speed and reliability of storage, while significantly changing the way of thinking of a specialist and the nature of professional activity.

It is no secret to whom it is a requirement today to carry out systematic work on the development of information and communication technologies in the region, ensuring their widespread use in the regions, institutions and organizations, enterprises.

Modern methods of training specialists with a competitive competence, high intellectual potential and comprehensively thoughtful thinking are one of the most important problems for the effective socio-economic development of the country. A competent approach is aimed at the formation of social, communicative, informational, professional and other personal qualities of the educational institution, which makes it possible to almost fully realize modern socio-economic conditions in itself. This approach is based on such a system of competencies as the formation of an opportunity to fully educate the personality of educators and solve important practical tasks.

On the basis of a competent approach lies the culture of self-determination (self-development of self-esteem, preparation for self-realization and the formation of competence). Professional developing specialist some kind of innovation in his profession (innovation), the creation of new technologies, including existing new techniques. Will be able to work with methods and others.

The purpose of the competency approach is to ensure the quality of education in the form of a team. An analysis of the work carried out internationally on the problems of improving the educational system shows that in updating the content of

education, the concepts of "competence" and "competence" are considered as the main units.

Professional competence is the acquisition by a specialist of the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of professional activities and the ability to apply them at a high level in practice.

Professional competence implies not the acquisition by a specialist of special knowledge, skills, but the assimilation of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. The competence also requires the constant enrichment of specialist knowledge, the study of new information, the ability to understand important social requirements, the search for new information, the ability to process and apply them in their activities.

Professional competence is clearly manifested in the following cases:

- in complex processes;
- when performing ambiguous tasks;
- when using conflicting information;
- when being able to have a plan of action in an unexpected situation

Specialist with professional competence:

- consistently enriches his knowledge;
- absorbs new information;
- clearly understands the requirements of the period;
- seeks new knowledge, processes them and effectively functions in its practical activities.

A theoretical analysis of the state of the problem of the formation and improvement of professional competence made it possible to draw the following conclusions: the professional creativity of the future mahandis-builder is a complex structure of the personality, which determines its functioning. Universal, professional knowledge, skills, skills, professional creative approach, social

cohesion of the individual, in general, the effect of professional tasks is a complex that provides a solution.

The introduction of new requirements to the quality of training of graduates of higher educational institutions into state educational standards led to the appeal to the following concepts: competence, components, cognitive competence, creative professional competence, competence in education development and implementation of the main tasks of a professional approach in the training of specialists for the multilateral intellectual and spiritual development of, within the framework of a new approach. In modern scientific and pedagogical literature and dissertation research, there are different interpretations of the concepts of competence and competence. The core of competence is knowledge. In addition, knowledge as a characteristic of competence has two components: theoretical and practical. The competence approach in education implies the formation of the main competencies of students.

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